

BE-SMART: THERMAL IMPACT OF PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULES BUILDING INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT: The Be-Smart project aims to contribute significantly to the strengthening of the European industrial sector in the field of solar energy and to present and demonstrate new concepts of low-cost photovoltaic (PV) products for building integration (BIPV) with a high quality architectural design (transparency, color...) named Energy positive Glasses or EpoGs. For a relevant choice of these products installation configuration, an experimental study of the impact of various parameters (see IEC TS 63126 standard) on the temperature of photovoltaic glass-glass monocrystalline silicon mini-modules is being performed for nearly one year on five different sites. A comparative analysis of first results obtained at the CEA INES site and the CEA Cadarache site is presented focusing on their maximum and their 98th percentile temperatures from December 2020 to May 2021. This most representative temperature should be considered to define EpoGs installation configuration per site. For facade integration, in cold period, the glass layers thickness seems to have an influence on photovoltaic modules temperature. As further studies, data measured in warm period will be analyzed. Then, in order to consider edges effect, similar tests will be performed on large PV modules integrated to a facade at the CEA INES site.

Keywords: Building Integrated PV (BIPV), Monitoring, Thermal behaviour

1 INTRODUCTION

The Be-Smart project aims to contribute significantly to the strengthening of the European industrial sector in the field of solar energy and to present new concepts of low-cost photovoltaic products for building integration (BIPV) with a high quality architectural design (transparency, color...). For this, colored glass-glass photovoltaic modules named Energy positive glass or EpoGs suitable especially for façade integration are designed and demonstrated in different sites in Europe. Since building integration of photovoltaic systems has a huge impact on their operating temperature [2], the knowledge of the thermal behaviour of the developed products is necessary in order to optimize the selection of the relevant installation configuration per site. Thus, an experimental study of the impact of various parameters on photovoltaic modules temperature is being performed for nearly one year on five sites with different climates (in France, in Switzerland, in Norway and in Cyprus). The influence of the mounting configuration, of the photovoltaic module glass thickness and of the climatic conditions are considered. Eighteen small size frameless monocrystalline silicon glass-glass photovoltaic modules laminated with 3.2 mm or 6 mm of glass layers were fixed on a south-oriented metal test bench according to three mounting configurations in line with the IEC TS 63126 standard (non-insulated, insulated and naturally ventilated) and three slopes (0°, 45° and 90°). This paper presents a comparative analysis of first results obtained at the CEA INES site and the CEA Cadarache site from December 2020 to May 2021 focusing on their maximum and their 98th percentile temperatures.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

2.1 Design of configurations

The photovoltaic modules mounting configuration and glass layer thickness and the climatic conditions are mainly taken into account during this study in order to optimize the choice of building integration configuration per site. The general design of the configurations to test was proposed in the framework of the Be-Smart project [2] and adapted by each partner to his site specificities.

The temperature at the 98th percentile (noted *T*₉₈, here) considered for this analysis is the one that a PV module will reach or exceed for only 2% of the year (or 175.2h). [3]

2.2 Presentation of test benches at the CEA sites

On each site, a metal mounting structure was ground-mounted considering the site shadings and albedo effects (see Fig. 1). Eighteen (18) small size frameless photovoltaic modules comprising 3.2 mm or 6 mm glass layers were fixed on this structure:

- Six non-insulated photovoltaic modules were taken as reference.
- Then, six modules comprised a 3 cm-thick air gap insulated with 14 cm of extruded polystyrene layer.
- Finally, six modules were insulated at the rear side.

Relevant spacing and disposal of PV modules were defined in order to reduce heat transfers between configurations especially due to air heating in the configuration with the insulated air gap. Each 6 Wp PV mini-module had a dimension of 20 cm x 20 cm and was connected to two electrical resistors T10 0.1 Ohm in parallel in order to maintain operating conditions close to the maximum power point.

Figure 1: Photograph of the eighteen photovoltaic modules mounted on the test bench at CEA INES site at Le Bourget du Lac and instrumentation (weather station and thermocouples).

The instrumentation was defined in order to permit the monitoring of weather data (ambient temperature with a PT100 sensor sheltered from solar radiation, wind direction and velocity with a weather vane and an anemometer, and solar radiation in the three planes considered using pyranometers). Temperatures inside and at the backside of photovoltaic modules (with K-type thermocouples) and electrical open circuit voltages were measured.

Prior to their installation, preliminary tests were performed (flash-test and electroluminescence). The K-type thermocouples used were calibrated between -10°C and 90°C with a thermostatic bath and the consistency of the readings of pyranometers was evaluated. Moreover, a solution for the installation of a thermocouple within the photovoltaic modules permitting to avoid breakage during lamination was defined. All sensors were connected to an Agilent data logger and the monitoring was realized with a 5 min time step since March 2019.

3 ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The impact of the site weather conditions was studied taking into account data measured at the CEA INES site and the CEA Cadarache site from December 2020 to March 2021. Moreover, most favorable mounting configurations were proposed on both sites for the month of December 2020.

3.1 Impact of the site weather conditions from December 2020 to March 2021

A comparative thermal analysis was carried out on the six first months of the test campaign focusing on their maximum (T_{max}) and their 98th percentile temperatures from December 2020 to May 2021.

Table I summarizes the results obtained with the BIPV configurations comprising an insulated air gap on the underside, two 3.2 mm thick glass layers and tilted at 45° or at 90° . (See table I)

Table I: Intervals of maximum temperatures and 98th percentile temperatures of the tilted and the vertical ventilated BIPV mini-module with 3.2 mm thick glass layers in December 2020 at the CEA INES site (a and b, respectively) and the CEA Cadarache site (c and d, respectively).

	CEA INES ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	CEA Cadarache ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
Tilted at 45°	T_{max} : [35.5 ; 54.5]	T_{max} : [36.2 ; 51.2]
	T_{98} : [24.8 ; 45.8]	T_{98} : [31.4 ; 43.2]
Vertical	T_{max} : [35.3 ; 45.8]	T_{max} : [36.2 ; 46.3]
	T_{98} : [24.4 ; 39.0]	T_{98} : [31.5 ; 37.6]

Between December 2020 and May 2021, T_{max} values of the tilted BIPV mini-module were between 35.5°C and 54.5°C , and its T_{98} values between 24.8°C and 45.8°C at the CEA INES site. Concerning the vertical BIPV mini-module, its T_{max} values were between 35.3°C and 45.8°C and its T_{98} values between 24.4°C and 39.0°C . At the CEA Cadarache site, its T_{max} values were between 36.2°C and 51.2°C and its T_{98} values were between 31.4°C and 43.2°C . For the vertical system, its T_{max} values were between 35.3°C and 45.8°C and its T_{98} between 24.4°C and 39.0°C .

3.2 Impact of the site weather conditions in December 2020

Figure 2 shows the maximum and 98th percentile temperatures in December 2020 for all configurations mounted at the CEA INES (see Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b) and the CEA Cadarache site (see Fig. 2c and Fig. 2d). Solar energy values received according to PV modules slope (vertical, 45° and horizontal) were of 38.7 kWh/m^2 , 22.27 kWh/m^2 and 34.09 kWh/m^2 , respectively at the CEA INES site and of 65.50 kWh/m^2 , 96.62 kWh/m^2 and 76.55 kWh/m^2 , respectively at the CEA Cadarache site.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Maximum temperatures and 98th percentile temperatures of the PV mini-modules in December 2020 at the CEA INES site (a and b respectively) and the CEA Cadarache site (c and d respectively) (with no iso: non-insulated; iso + air gap: with an insulated air gap at the underside; iso: insulated at the underside).

Results of December 2020 have shown that the 98th percentile temperature (T_{98}) is lower than the maximum temperature (T_{max}) for all the configurations studied and T_{max} is most the time, a peak value, as expected. Only 2% of PV module temperatures are between T_{98} and T_{max} . T_{98} should therefore be considered for the optimum installation of EpoGs per site.

The difference between T_{max} and T_{98} was between 4.3°C and 11.5°C at the CEA INES site and between 2.4°C and 8°C at the CEA Cadarache site. Higher temperature were observed for PV modules inclined at 45° and vertical PV modules compared to horizontal modules. This could be due to their lower angle of incidence in cold periods (lower sun height) leading to most important temperature levels.

The maximum temperatures and the T_{98} values of PV modules at the CEA Cadarache site were generally higher than the ones measured at the CEA INES site, as expected, due to a higher solar radiation level. The difference between T_{max} values of the two sites was between 6.6°C and 29.7°C. This difference was between 11°C and 28°C for T_{98} , which is important.

The smaller differences observed in the case of vertical modules in both sites could be explained by a better solar exposure during the cold period, which increases their heating.

At the CEA INES site, the horizontal non-insulated and non-integrated PV configuration (with 3.2 mm- thick glass layers) was the most favorable at the thermal level (with

T_{max} value of 18.2°C and T_{98} value of 13.5°C) due to an optimum natural ventilation at the underside of the PV module. For a vertical integration, ventilated BIPV mini-modules with 6 mm- thick glass layers were the most suitable (with T_{max} value of 33.2°C and T_{98} value of 22.8°C).

Then, at the CEA Cadarache site, the horizontal ventilated BIPV configuration with 6 mm- thick glass layers was the most favorable (with T_{max} value of 40.8°C and T_{98} value of 35.7°C) due, among other to higher angles of incidence of solar radiation in cold periods (low sun height). For a vertical integration, ventilated BIPV mini-modules with 3.2 mm- thick glass layers were the most suitable (with T_{max} value of 41.8°C and T_{98} value of 37.2°C).

4 CONCLUSION

Only 2% of photovoltaic module temperatures are between their maximum and their 98th percentile temperatures. Thus, the 98th percentile temperatures is a relevant parameter for the choice of the optimum installation configuration of EpoGs products per site. For facade integration, according to a cold month results, the choice of glass layers thickness seems to have an influence on the PV modules thermal behaviour. This comparison has shown that on both sites, the most favorable configuration varies per month, so a study on an annual base is required.

As further studies, a similar comparative analysis will be carried out on six months in warm period in order to validate these first observations and to define optimal configurations per site at the annual level. Finally, a similar study will also be performed on large PV modules integrated on a facade at the CEA INES site in order to take account edge effects.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work realized within INES.2S was partially supported by the French state under the Investments for the Future programme (ANR-10-IEED-0014-01). It has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 818009

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